

Considerations For Streamlining The FCC Equipment Authorization Program

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ABSTRACT

Certain radio frequency (rf) devices require approval by the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) before they may be imported and marketed in the United States. There is growing interest in streamlining mandatory equipment approval processes for a number of reasons. This paper will describe the current FCC equipment authorization requirements and a new FCC proposal to streamline and simplify its equipment approval processes, including the expansion of Declaration of Conformity to other types of equipment. The paper goes on to describe various steps taken by the FCC Laboratory staff to improve speed of service with the introduction of electronic filing and extensive use of electronic mail messages.

INTRODUCTION

In 1970, the FCC established an equipment authorization program to ensure that rf devices, such as transmitters, receivers, computers and other electronic products, meet standards that are designed to control rf interference. For a number of reasons, these equipment authorization procedures have become complicated, confusing and in some cases burdensome. On March 13, 1997, the FCC adopted a Notice of Proposed Rulemaking in ET Docket 97-94, to streamline its equipment authorization procedures. All interested parties were invited to comment on the proposal. Specifically, it proposes to amend Parts 2, 15, 18 and other rule parts to: 1) simplify our existing equipment authorization processes; 2) deregulate the equipment authorization requirements for certain types of equipment; and 3) provide for electronic filing of applications for equipment authorization.

BACKGROUND

Section 302 of the Communications Act of 1934, was adopted with the clear purpose of ensuring that radio transmitters and electronic devices meet standards to control radio interference before such equipment reaches the marketplace. This section authorizes the FCC, consistent with the public interest, convenience, and necessity, to make reasonable regulations governing the interference potential of devices which in their operation are capable of emitting radio frequency energy by radiation, conduction, or other means in sufficient degree to cause harmful interference to radio communications. Further, no

person shall manufacture, import, sell, offer for sale, or ship devices or use devices that fail to comply with regulations promulgated under this section. Prior to adoption of this section, there had been numerous instances of devices that had reached the marketplace in massive quantities and caused widespread interference to radio communications. It was impractical and inefficient to attempt to resolve interference caused by such devices on a case-by-case basis. Moreover, often the only way to resolve the interference was to require that operation of the device cease or that the device be modified, at great inconvenience and expense to consumers. More important, radio frequency devices often posed an unacceptable risk of interference to vital safety communications, such as police and fire communications and aeronautical and maritime navigation systems.

The FCC has carried out its responsibilities under Section 302 through two principal means. First, the Commission has established technical regulations for radio transmitters and certain electronic equipment to control radio frequency interference. Second, the FCC has required such devices to be authorized to ensure that the equipment meets the technical requirements. The equipment authorization process is accomplished largely through the use of the private sector. That is, the manufacturer tests the product to determine whether it meets the technical requirements. In many cases the manufacturer self-approves its equipment. However, for certain types of equipment that have been found to pose a strong risk of noncompliance, the FCC requires submission of a written application for equipment authorization. The FCC may request a sample of the device to check the results; however, this is done in a small minority of cases.

The FCC's equipment authorization program has been a resounding success in controlling interference. Today, hundreds of millions of radio transmitters, consumer products and electronic devices all share the airwaves with remarkably little interference. Continuing to ensure compliance with our technical requirements through the equipment authorization program is even more important for the future. The radio spectrum is becoming ever more crowded as new radio services are added and existing services continue to grow. The FCC recognizes that companies are making enormous investments to obtain licenses to use the spectrum and to construct communications systems. These investments and the success of

new services could easily be jeopardized by the threat of radio frequency interference. We note, in particular, that concerns about interference exist in many areas, such as interference to hearing aids from wireless equipment, interference to medical devices, interference to aeronautical communications from carry-on consumer electronic devices, and interference at mobile radio antenna sites. We also note that vital policy objectives, such as controlling the environmental effects of radio frequency radiation, closed captioning of TV receivers, compatibility of TV receivers with cable systems, and prohibitions against scanning receivers that are capable of receiving cellular radio transmissions, are being ensured in whole or in part through the equipment authorization program. We believe that the equipment authorization program remains essential to the FCC's mission.

The current FCC equipment authorization procedures have evolved over the course of more than 25 years. The multiplicity of equipment authorization processes has resulted in an extensive and complicated set of regulations which were adopted in 1970 and have since changed many times. Manufacturers are often confused as to the requirements and procedures they must follow, which can sometimes lead to delays in introducing products to the market. Such delays can cause a manufacturer to lose its competitive advantage. The fast pace of today's telecommunications and electronics industries has heightened the need for equipment authorization procedures that are clear, rapid and efficient. Accordingly, the FCC initiated the proposal to provide a simpler, less burdensome path for products to be marketed in the United States. The FCC solicited as broad a range of comments and alternative suggestions as possible. The following is a description of the present equipment authorization procedures and an overview of the specific proposals.

EXISTING EQUIPMENT AUTHORIZATION PROCESSES

The FCC rules specify technical requirements for radio and electronic equipment to control radio frequency interference. Part 15, for example, contains technical requirements for unintentional and intentional radiators; Part 22 contains technical requirements for transmitters used in the commercial mobile radio services; and, Part 90 specifies the technical requirements for transmitters used in the private land mobile radio services. In some cases devices must meet technical requirements that are not related to interference. For example, TV receivers with screen sizes greater than 13" must be capable of displaying closed captioning. Also, certain radio transmitters must demonstrate compliance with standards designed to protect against harmful biological effects from exposure to radio frequency energy. In order to ensure compliance with the technical requirements, the rules generally require the equipment to be authorized in accordance with one of the procedures in Part 2 Subpart J of the rules. The equipment authorization procedures are as follows:

Type acceptance is an equipment authorization issued by the Commission for equipment to be used pursuant to a station authorization (i.e., in authorized radio services such as commercial and private land mobile radio services). Type acceptance is based on submittal of a written application that includes a complete technical description of the product and a test report showing compliance with the technical requirements. This procedure has been used for most equipment operating in the "authorized" radio services (i.e., including those licensed individually or covered by a blanket license or rule).

Certification is an equipment authorization issued by the Commission for equipment designed to be operated without an individual license under Parts 15 and 18 of the rules. Certification is based on submittal of a written application that includes a complete technical description of the product and a test report showing compliance with the technical requirements. In this regard, the process is very similar to type acceptance; however, the nature of the technical requirements for equipment operated under Parts 15 and 18 tends to differ significantly from the requirements for equipment used in authorized radio services. Devices operating under Parts 15 and 18 generally must meet limits on radiated and power line conducted emissions. Transmitters operating in the authorized radio services generally must meet requirements for output power, frequency stability, out-of-band and spurious emissions, etc.

Notification is an equipment authorization issued by the Commission whereby the applicant makes measurements to determine that the equipment complies with the appropriate technical standards and submits a report that such measurements have been made and that the equipment demonstrates the necessary compliance. Submittal of test data to the Commission demonstrating compliance is not required unless specifically requested by the Commission. Notification has been applied to a variety of equipment where there is a reasonably good likelihood of compliance.

Verification is a manufacturer self-approval procedure where the manufacturer makes measurements or takes the necessary steps to ensure that the equipment complies with the appropriate technical standards.

Declaration of Conformity (DoC) is a relatively new self-approval procedure that also calls for the manufacturer or importer of the equipment to make measurements or take other necessary steps to ensure that the equipment complies with the appropriate technical standards. This procedure was established in 1996 in connection with the FCC's deregulation (ET Docket 95-19) of the certification requirements for personal computer equipment. A statement declaring that the equipment complies with the FCC rules must be included in the literature furnished with the product. The test laboratory performing the compliance measurements must be accredited by either the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) or the American Association for Laboratory Accreditation (A2LA).

Applications for equipment authorization are processed at the FCC Laboratory in Columbia, Maryland. Applications are usually processed in about 40 days, but can take longer if additional information must be submitted to complete or correct the application. The FCC Laboratory may request a sample device for testing, either in connection with an application for equipment authorization or once a product has been placed on the market. The equipment authorization process must be completed before importation and marketing can begin, pursuant to the FCC marketing rules (Subpart I of Part 2). As noted, there are currently several different equipment authorization processes. It is believed that certain of these processes can be eliminated and others combined to greatly simplify the requirements, eliminate unnecessary rules and reduce regulatory burdens. The specific FCC proposals are discussed below.

The type acceptance and certification procedures are similar in many respects. They both involve submittal of a written application, technical description of the equipment, measurement report showing compliance with the technical standards, photographs of the equipment and certain other information. The principal difference between the procedures, as noted above, is that type acceptance has usually applied to equipment operating in the authorized radio services, while certification has usually applied to equipment operating under Parts 15 and 18. We observe, however, that this distinction is becoming less clear. For example, the Commission recently required transmitters operating in the Family Radio Service under Part 95 of the rules to be certificated. We believe that there would be several benefits if the certification and type acceptance procedures were combined into one procedure. The regulations would be simplified by eliminating duplicative requirements. We believe that simpler rules would reduce errors that lead to deficient applications and noncompliance. Where the rules currently require multiple applications for certain equipment, a single application would suffice. Accordingly, the FCC proposed to eliminate the type acceptance procedure and incorporate into the certification procedure those requirements that continue to be necessary for equipment used in the authorized services. It is appropriate to maintain use of the term certification because this term is used internationally for similar procedures.

We recognize that there are several similar rule sections under the type acceptance and certification procedures, such as the requirements for information that must be included in an application and for permissive changes. We proposed generally to supplement the existing certification rules with any additional information that may continue to be needed for equipment used in the authorized radio services. We also noted that the current type acceptance procedures include considerable information on the required measurements; e.g., rf power output, modulation characteristics, occupied bandwidth, etc. We believe these regulations continue to be necessary. We propose to include these regulations under the certification procedure, but will

indicate that they apply only to equipment used in the authorized radio services.

The notification procedure was initially established in the 1980s for equipment that no longer warranted type acceptance or certification, but still posed sufficient risk of noncompliance to monitor the introduction of new products. Therefore, the notification procedure required submittal of a written application, but without technical data. It was believed that by monitoring equipment through the application process, potential compliance problems could be identified quickly and technical data could be requested as necessary. It was expected that compliance would also be facilitated by having the name and address of the party responsible for compliance. The FCC reported that there has been little benefit from the notification procedure. Equipment that is currently subject to notification has rarely exhibited any compliance problems. However, such applications have sometimes experienced delays in the equipment authorization process due to minor administrative errors. The FCC does not believe the benefit from review of such applications warrants the delays that can result. Accordingly, the Commission proposed to delete the notification procedure. Also, it proposed that equipment formerly subject to notification would instead be subject to either the DoC or verification procedure, with the specific proposals given below.

It was noted in the proposal that the verification and DoC procedures are also similar in that they are both manufacturer self-authorization procedures. However, there are several important differences. The DoC procedure requires use of an accredited test laboratory; the verification procedure requires only that the laboratory retain a description of its measurement facilities. The DoC procedure requires the manufacturer to include a written Declaration of Compliance with the literature furnished to the user, in part as a means to identify the party responsible for FCC compliance; no information is required to be provided to the user for verified equipment. The DoC procedure requires use of an FCC logo on the equipment identification label to promote compliance by providing a means for consumers to identify equipment that meets FCC regulations; verification requires only that the equipment be uniquely identified. There are a number of other minor differences between the two sets of rules.

The FCC proposed to maintain both the DoC and verification procedures. The DoC procedure was established only recently and any further changes at this time would be disruptive. Further, it was noted that the verification procedure provides a means to authorize equipment that imposes very little burden on manufacturers. We believe such a procedure is appropriate for equipment that has an excellent record of compliance, where the measurement methods are well known and understood, and it is relatively easy to determine the party responsible for compliance. Nevertheless, comments were solicited as to whether we should maintain DoC and verification as separate procedures or whether there may be some benefit in combining

these procedures in some fashion. For example, one option would be to eliminate verification, shift all the equipment to the DoC procedure, and exempt certain equipment from the requirement to use an accredited test laboratory.

As noted below, the FCC proposed placing greater reliance on use of the DoC and verification processes, which will lessen the burden on manufacturers. We believe that some changes in the rules are needed to improve oversight of the compliance of equipment on the market. Under Section 2.946 of the rules, any responsible party, or any party who markets equipment subject to the rules has up to 60 days to provide a test sample upon request by the Commission. When equipment is widely available on the U.S. market, 60 days is an unreasonable period to wait for submittal of a sample, particularly where the Commission may have cause to suspect that a particular piece of equipment does not meet FCC technical standards. Accordingly, for equipment that is widely available on the market we are proposing to require submittal of a sample to the Commission for testing within 14 days of request. To accomplish this, we are proposing to require manufacturers to provide a voucher upon request for purchase of a sample equipment at a retail outlet. Besides comments on this proposal, interested parties were also invited to provide alternative suggestions for improving oversight of equipment on the market.

DEREGULATION OF EQUIPMENT AUTHORIZATION REQUIREMENTS FOR VARIOUS EQUIPMENT

The list of equipment subject to an equipment authorization is long and complicated. The list is presented in Appendix C of the Proposal, but is not repeated here to save space. It was reported in the Proposal that the equipment authorization requirements for many types of equipment have not been reviewed for 10 years or longer. The FCC stated that submittal and review of equipment authorization applications to the Commission are no longer warranted for certain equipment where the technical requirements are met with little difficulty, the test methods are widely understood, interpretive questions arise infrequently, and there has been an excellent record of compliance. Accordingly, it was proposed to relax the equipment authorization requirements for various types of equipment based on FCC experience in reviewing applications and our assessment of the appropriate procedure required to ensure continued compliance. The Commission recognized that there currently is no laboratory accreditation available for tests on certain of the equipment proposed to be shifted to the DoC procedure; however, we believe that accrediting organizations such as the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and the American Association for Laboratory Accreditation (A2LA) can establish an accreditation process for tests on such products if the demand exists. The specific FCC proposals are as follows:

1. Relax the requirements from certification or notification to the DoC procedure for the following Part 15 unintentional radiators: CB receivers; superregenerative receivers; all other Part 15 receivers; and, TV Interface Devices (including video cassette recorders and TV video games), except that we will require certification for cable system terminal devices to ensure against marketing of such devices for theft of cable service. The FCC proposed to continue to require certification for scanning receivers to ensure that they meet the Congressionally mandated requirement of Section 15.121 that they do not tune to frequencies allocated to the Domestic Public Cellular Radio Telecommunications Service.
2. Relax the requirements for Part 18 consumer ISM (industrial, scientific and medical) equipment from certification to the DoC procedure. This includes such devices as consumer microwave ovens, rf lighting devices, and ultrasonic jewelry cleaners.
3. Relax the requirements for wildlife tracking and ocean buoys operating under Part 5 from notification to verification. [Note: The Commission proposed in ET Docket 96-256, adopted 12/17/96, to move this service to Part 90.]
4. Relax the requirements for Part 101 point-to-point microwave transmitters from notification to the DoC procedure.
5. Relax the requirements for Part 73 standard broadcast (AM transmitters), FM transmitters, television transmitters, and antenna phase monitors from notification to verification. AM stereo transmitters are currently subject to type acceptance. Under this proposal such equipment will fall under the certification procedure.
6. Relax the requirements for Auxiliary Broadcast aural STLs, aural intercity relays, aural STL boosters, aural intercity relay boosters, TV STLs, TV intercity relays, TV translator relays and TV microwave boosters from notification to the DoC procedure.
7. Relax the requirements for Part 78 Cable Television Relay fixed transmitters from notification to the DoC procedure.
8. Relax the requirement for Part 80 INMARSAT equipment from notification to verification.
9. Relax the requirement for Part 87, 406 Mhz emergency locator transmitters from notification to verification.

10. No changes for equipment that is currently subject to either the DoC or verification procedures. Specifically, the following equipment would remain subject to verification: digital devices (other than personal computer equipment); FM and TV broadcast receivers; non-consumer ISM equipment; and stand-alone cable input selector switches. Personal computer equipment can continue to be authorized under the DoC procedure.

The Commission proposed to retain the certification requirements for Part 15 intentional radiators, including spread spectrum devices, cordless telephones, remote control and security devices, field disturbance sensors, unlicensed PCS (Personal Communications Service) devices and NII (National Information Infrastructure) devices. We frequently found significant problems in the review of applications for certification of such devices. Further, it has been the FCC Laboratory's experience that such applications frequently raise questions concerning interpretation of the intent of the regulations. We believe that compliance with the regulations would sharply decline in the absence of a Commission pre-market review. This would pose an unacceptable risk of millions of devices entering the marketplace that are capable of causing widespread interference to communications services, including safety and radionavigation services. It is far more efficient to ensure that such products comply with the FCC requirements before they reach the market than to attempt to locate and correct hundreds or even thousands of cases of interference. The Proposal noted also that interference from such devices has the potential to thwart new communications services in spectrum for which licensees have made sizeable investments. The Commission stated that the small burden of certification is warranted in order to protect the valuable spectrum resource.

The FCC proposed to shift all equipment currently subject to type acceptance to the certification procedure. This is simply an administrative change and will not lower the threshold of review for compliance with the technical requirements. It was noted that there have recently been significant changes in the technical requirements for much of the equipment subject to type acceptance. For example, new spectrum efficiency requirements have been specified for transmitters operating in several private land mobile frequency bands. It was also observed that certain equipment currently subject to type acceptance must meet new rf exposure guidelines, adopted in FCC ET Docket 93-62, released on August 1, 1997, FCC 96-326. Continuing Commission oversight through review of applications is essential to the implementation of these requirements. The Proposal noted that new technologies, such as narrowband and broadband personal communications services, have given rise to significant technical and legal interpretation questions that affect compliance and fair competition among manufacturers and technologies. Therefore, the Commission does not believe that relaxation of the review process is appropriate for equipment currently subject to type acceptance. Here again, it is believed that the risks of interference outweigh the small burden of the

equipment authorization process. Comments were invited, however, as to whether certain equipment that is currently subject to type acceptance might be relaxed to the DoC or verification processes.

Comments were also invited on the specific proposals for changing the equipment authorization requirements for various equipment. In particular, the FCC solicited information as to whether any equipment currently subject to certification or notification should be relaxed to a different procedure than was proposed. Recommendations were also invited as to whether any equipment proposed to be subject to certification should be relaxed to the DoC or verification procedures.

The Commission proposed to permit applicants to file under the existing procedures for a period of up to two years. It was also proposed to discontinue accepting applications for certification of personal computer equipment at that time since such equipment can be authorized under the DoC procedure. It was stated that continuing to authorize equipment under the existing procedures indefinitely would require the Commission to maintain resources for this activity unnecessarily. Further, allowing multiple authorization procedures for specific equipment indefinitely will lead to confusion. Comments were solicited on the proposed transition plan and alterations thereto.

ELECTRONIC FILING OF EQUIPMENT AUTHORIZATION APPLICATIONS

The Commission stated that it was committed to continually improving the processing of applications for equipment authorization that are required to be submitted to the Commission. We believe the existing process can be streamlined significantly by providing for the electronic filing of such applications. This action would improve the speed with which applications may be filed with the Commission, the accuracy of data input for application processing, the speed of application processing, and the accessibility of equipment authorization information to the public. The FCC stated that it anticipated that the current application processing time of approximately 40 days can be reduced by at least half through these measures. The Commission has engaged a contractor to perform a preliminary requirements analysis and initial system design for the electronic filing of such applications. At the time of the proposal, the FCC did not know precisely when it will initiate electronic filing of applications for certification. The Commission will issue a public notice announcing the acceptance of electronically filed applications at the appropriate time. The Commission also is proposing to recognize electronic signatures on applications. There are also a number of other issues that the Commission believes should be examined before implementing electronic filing of applications.

It appears that the most effective means to implement electronic filing would be through the use of the Internet. Initial system design proposes that an application would be completed via an

Internet web page located on an FCC Internet server. Attachments, including all exhibits required by the Commission's rules such as manuals, diagrams, photographs, etc., would be copied to a specified FCC file server using file transfer protocol (ftp). Exhibits would follow a standard submission format, and be submitted using tagged image format (tif) files and/or portable document format (pdf) files. Fees would be paid either by check or by credit card. The application process would be paperless and could be accomplished in a more timely manner since it would be concurrent with fee collection and validation, and some of the examining and technical review functions could be done in parallel. Information on the status of pending applications would be immediately available to the applicant, and information on granted applications and other equipment authorization information would be immediately available to the general public.

The FCC is considering whether to require that all equipment authorization applications be filed electronically. While it is recognized that not all applicants would have on-site access to equipment that would permit electronic filing, the Commission believes that a majority of equipment authorization applicants are on the "cutting edge" of technology, and would have ready access to equipment and software to permit them to file electronically. Furthermore, this function could be incorporated into the service provided by testing laboratories, or could be performed by many of the private companies that are available for digitizing and electronically transmitting photographs and documents. The benefits to the applicant would be seen in an improved speed of service due to more timely application receipt, as well as an increase in processing resources that would be freed from data input and paper file management. Comments were invited on the possible complete elimination of paper applications.

The Commission frequently receives requests to examine and copy applications for equipment authorization after they have been granted. If implemented, the proposed electronic filing initiative would result in digitized storage of all equipment authorization application information. The Commission is considering how it can best make the applications available to the public once they are granted. [The Commission would of course continue to apply all the regulations pertaining to inspection of records and granting of confidentiality in accordance with 47 CFR Section 0.451, et seq.] While all application information could be made available via the Internet, the Commission is concerned that the volume of information contained in each application could cause an overall degradation of service to users. An alternative would be to provide via the Internet the information that users consider most useful, such as the application Form 731, and designate an outside contractor that could provide the remaining information upon request. Specific comments were requested on this approach and whether certain other basic information such as the measurement report should be made available over the Internet. The Proposal also

solicited views on the vehicle and media that is most beneficial for distributing application information.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The above is a condensed version of the FCC Proposal to streamline its equipment authorization program. The proposal if adopted would: 1) simplify current equipment authorization procedures; 2) liberalize the equipment authorization requirements for certain equipment; and, 3) provide for electronic filing of equipment authorization applications. Comments and alternative recommendations were solicited on all aspects of the equipment authorization requirements. Comments on the Proposal are expected to be received on or about July 9, 1997, and reply comments are expected 30 days later, unless there is an extension of the time period granted.

These actions, if adopted, were reported to greatly reduce the complexity and burden of the Commission's equipment authorization requirements. Further, these steps are expected to improve the efficiency of the equipment authorization process so that products can be introduced to the market more rapidly. They would reduce the number of applications required to be filed with the Commission annually from about 3500 to approximately 1800, significantly reducing paperwork requirements of manufacturers. A similar, previous action was estimated to save the computer industry \$250 million annually, and savings of at least another \$100 million can be expected for the products covered by the current proposal. The provision for electronic filing of applications should reduce by more than half the current applications processing time of approximately 40 days. We believe this proposal will greatly benefit both large and small manufacturers and encourage the development of innovative products that best meet consumers' needs.

One final comment that we are obliged to make. All comments and opinions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent those of the Commission or its staff.